

Predstavitev infrastrukture OPERAS in storitve GoTriple

Odkrivanje raziskovalnih rezultatov s področja družboslovja in humanistike

mag. Aleš Pogačnik, Založba ZRC, ZRC SAZU
Ana Inkret, Arhiv družboslovnih podatkov
mag. Irena Vipavc Brvar, Arhiv družboslovnih podatkov

Program

- Raziskovalna struktura OPERAS in nacionalno vozlišče, 5 min
- Storitve in projekti OPERAS, 10 min
- Predstavitev platforme GoTriple, 10 min
- Vprašanja in diskusija

Raziskovalna struktura OPERAS in slovensko nacionalno vozlišče

OPERAS je raziskovalna infrastruktura, ki podpira odprto znanstveno komuniciranje na področju družboslovja in humanistike (SSH) v Evropskem raziskovalnem prostoru (ERA). Njeno poslanstvo je usklajevanje in združevanje virov v Evropi za učinkovito zadovoljevanje potreb evropskih raziskovalcev po znanstvenem komuniciranju na področju SSH.

Max Weber
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Struktura OPERAS

POSEBNE INTERESNE SKUPINE

- Zagovor odprte znanosti (*Advocacy*)
- Najboljši primeri (*Best Practices*)
- Splošni standardi in načela FAIR (*Common Standards and FAIR Principles*)
- Večjezičnost (*Multilingualism*)
- Mreža knjig v odprtem dostopu (*Open Access Books Network*)
- Poslovni modeli odprtega dostopa (*Open Access Business Models*)
- Orodja in platforme (*Tools and Platforms*)

<https://operas-eu.org/special-interest-group-living-book/>

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Storitve OPERAS

<https://operas-eu.org/services/>

- GoTRIPLE: inovativna večjezična platforma za odkrivanje virov na področju družboslovja in humanistike;
[Gotriple.eu](https://gotriple.eu) (polno delujoča različica)
- Metrics: enotna točka dostopa do metrik, povezanih z monografijami v odprtem dostopu;
[Metrics.operas-eu.org](https://metrics.operas-eu.org) (beta različica, polna delujoča različica v začetku leta 2023)
- PRISM Peer Review: informacije o recenzentskem postopku posamezne monografije;
[Doabooks.org](https://doabooks.org) (polno delujoča različica)
- Pathfinder: enotni portal za odkrivanje storitev znanstvenega komuniciranja, ki jih zagotavljajo članice OPERAS;
pathfinder.unito.it (alfa, polno delujoča različica leta 2023)
- Hypotheses: platforma za blogse raziskovalcev s področja humanistike in družboslovja;
hypotheses.org (polno delujoča različica)
- Vera: platforma za sodelovanje, prek katere lahko različni akterji skupaj oblikujejo družboslovne in humanistične raziskovalne projekte; trenutno v beta različici, polno delujoča različica leta 2023
vera.operas-eu.org

Projekti OPERAS

<https://operas-eu.org/projects/>

DIAMAS

CRAFT-OA

eosc

Skills
4 eosc

OPERAS
PLUS

- DIAMAS (Developing Institutional Open Access Publishing Models to Advance Scholarly Communication): 23/12, od septembra 2022, EU
- CRAFT-OA (Creating a Robust Accessible Federated Technology for Open Access): 23/14, od januarja 2023, EU
- Palomera (Supporting the development of aligned policies for open access books and monographs): 26/8, od januarja 2023, EU
- OA Book Usage Data Trust: od julija 2022, Mellon Foundation
- COESO (Collaborative Engagement on Societal Issues): od januarja 2021, 15/5, EU
- Skills4EOSC: 44/18, od septembra 2022, EU; OPERAS WP5 Work Package 5: OS Skills for RIs and thematic communities
- SUES (Supporting Ukrainian Editorial Staff), EU: 5/3 in več kot 30 francoskih univerz
- OPERAS-PLUS: od septembra 2022, 13/12
- OPERAS-GER: od septembra 2020
- Translations and Open Science (enoletni, francosko ministrstvo)
- TRIPLE: januar 2019 – marec 2023
- OPERAS-D: januar 2017 – junij 2018
- OPERAS-P: julij 2019 – junij 2021
- Open Access Diamond: junij 2020 – februar 2021 (10, francosko ministrstvo)

Odkrij
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Vodi
projekte

Najdi
financiranje

Pridobi
vidnost

COESO
connecting research and society

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Overcoming obstacles that hinder the development of Citizen Science in the SSH

- **Supporting 10 Citizen Science pilots** representing a variety of disciplines, societal challenges and types of engagement with citizens.
- **Developing VERA (Virtual Ecosystem for Research Activation) platform** for the public to manage SSH citizen science projects, find partners, collaborate, & find funding: vera.operas-eu.org (beta version until Nov 2023)
- **Collaborating with research funding organizations** to enhance financial support to Citizen Science.
- **Increasing SSH citizen science visibility** by experimenting with blogging and other science communication practices.

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COESO project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation program under grant agreement No 101006325. The content of this publication is the sole responsibility of the COESO consortium and can in no way be taken to reflect the views of the European Commission. The European Commission is not responsible for any use that may be made of the information it contains.

Skiils 4 eosc

Ustvarjanje ekosistema usposabljanja za odprto in FAIR znanost

Sodelovanje

Učni načrt

Učenje

Potrdila

Usklajevanje

Usposabljanje

Strategija

Osnove OS in Podatkovno intenzivna znanost

Sinergija

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- Translations and Open Science (enoletni, francosko ministrstvo)
- TRIPLE: januar 2019 -- marec 2023
- OPERAS-D: januar 2017 -- junij 2018
- OPERAS-P: julij 2019 -- junij 2021
- Open Access Diamond: junij 2020 -- februar 2021 (10, francosko ministrstvo)

Članstvo v OPERAS

<https://operas-eu.org/about/want-to-know-more/want-to-join-operas/>

- nacionalni koordinator in član EA ima volilno pravico ter je dolžan plačevati letno članarino (5000 EUR)
- navadni član se obveže, da bo z 10 % FTE sodeloval v kateri od posebnih interesnih skupin
- članstvo mora potrditi EA, po opravljenem razgovoru

Več informacij

Aleš Pogačnik, koordinator OPERAS-SI, vodja in glavni urednik Založbe ZRC Znanstvenoraziskovalnega centra Slovenske akademije znanosti in umetnosti (ZRC SAZU), 014706454, ales.pogacnik@zrc-sazu.si

GoTriple

Discovery service for the social sciences and humanities

gotriple.eu

GoTriple je inovativna večjezična platforma za odkrivanje virov s področja družboslovja in humanistike.

Omogoča

- brskanje, iskanje, dostop in ponovno uporabo znanstvenih virov, razpršenih po lokalnih in področnih repozitorijih,
- vizualizacijo iskalnih rezultatov,
- prilagojena priporočila,
- dodajanje opomb v spletne dokumente,
- stik z raziskovalci in projekti preko disciplinarnih, kulturnih in jezikovnih meja,
- raziskovanje novih načinov financiranja raziskav.

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Triple

Delovanje

Viri

- agregatorji DOAB, DOAJ, ISIDORE, OpenAIRE, EKT SearchCulture.gr, BASE, CESSDA, centri CLARIN
- založniki, nacionalni in institucionalni ponudniki: HRČAK, Biblioteka Nauki, EKT publishing, EKT National Archive of PhD Theses, OAPEN, ZRC SAZU
- projekti: CORDIS, wemakeit, VERA

Obdelava metapodatkov dokumentov in projektov

- normalizacija metapodatkov
- prepoznavanje jezika
- prevod v angleški jezik
- klasifikacija
- dodajanje oznak iz besedišča TRIPLE
- odstranjevanje podvojenih dokumentov
- normalizacija in identifikacija avtorjev

Domača stran

gotriple.eu

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Search publications, data, projects and authors

Search

SEARCH TIPS : [femicide](#) [science ouverte](#) ["open access"](#) [\(fair OR "open access"\) AND publishing](#)

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Social Sciences and Humanities

8.210.404

21.823

6.921.495

Report an Issue

Iskanje in odkrivanje

2.726 results

Documents 2.719 Projects 7 People 0

Your Search

fishing

Search

Geography x

List

Visual

Knowledge Map [↗](#)
Get an overview of relevant concepts and documents

Streamgraph [↗](#)
Analyze trends over time and discover related documents

Sorting Relevance

Filter Documents

Discipline

Search

- Geography 2.719
- Environmental studies 1.830
- History 161
- Archaeology and Prehistory 103
- Sociology 95

Language

Statistics of the European Union and associated flags purse seine fishing fleet targeting tropical tunas in the Indian Ocean 1981-2014

[Chassot, Emmanuel](#), [Assan, C.](#), [Soto, M.](#) +8 authors
Text, 2015-01-01

Assessing the effect of marine isoprene and ship emissions on ozone, using modelling and measurements from the South Atlantic Ocean

[Williams, J.](#), [Custer, T.](#), [Riede, H.](#) +16 authors
Text, 2010-01-01

Ship-borne measurements have been made in air over the remote South Atlantic and Southern Oceans in January-March 2007. This cruise encountered a large-scale natural phytoplankton bloom emitting reactive hydrocarbons (e. g. isoprene); and a high seas squid fishing fleet emitting NOx (N...

Vizualizacija - Streamgraph

Vizualizacija - Knowledge maps

Knowledge Map of **fishing**
100 most relevant documents | Data source: GoTrip... | 1 Jan 1922 - 12 Apr 2023 | Document types | All languages | Data quality | [More information](#)

The knowledge map consists of several interconnected nodes, each representing a research topic. The nodes include: 'Fishing license, Resource /energy Economics and policy, Willingness to pay', 'Unreported and unregulated fishing (IUU fishing), Illegal unreported, Lake Victoria', 'Pencegahan illegal fishing, Law enforcement, Agriculture', 'Saltwater recreational fishing trips, Count data, ...', 'Fish aggregating devices, Video monitoring, Biga Peninsula', 'Recreational fishing, Fishing community, Catch statistics', 'Artisanal fishers, Artisanal fishing, Coastal communities', 'Poverty, Assets, Ecology', 'Fishing effort, Geographical distribution, Fishing moratorium', 'Fishing gears, Traditional fishing, Cultural heritage', and 'Fishing tourism, Miryoku engineering, Southern Taiwan'. A central node is labeled 'fishing fishing rod; Chronicle Ruthenians; Gallus Anonymus...'. A 'Cite' button is visible on the left side of the map.

Overview (100 documents)

Search within visualization... | show: Any | sort by: Relevance

journal/newspaper article

The value of recreational fishing in Sweden - Estimates based on a nationwide survey (2021-01-01)

Ola Carlen, Kjell Göran Bostedt, Runar Brännlund, Lars Persson
[link]: https://pub.epsilon.slu.se/24984/1/carlen_o_et_al_210823.pdf

A nationwide recreational fishing survey in Sweden was used to estimate the benefits of recreational fishing in Sweden. The survey targeted the Swedish population and, consequently, the sample contained a large fraction of zero fishing days. To consider this, a zero-inflated Poisson...

Cite as | Export

Area: Recreational fishing, Fishing community, Catch statistics

journal/newspaper article

Improving fisheries estimates by including women's catch in the Central Philippines (2014-01-01)

Danika Kleiber, Lella Harris, Amanda Vincent
[link]: https://researchonline.jcu.edu.au/56000/1/56000_Kleiber_et_al_2014.pdf

Small-scale fisheries catch and effort estimates are often built on incomplete data because they overlook the fishing of minority or marginalized groups. Women do participate in small-scale fisheries and often in ways distinct from men's fishing. Hence, the inclusion of women's fishing ...

Cite as | Export

Area: Fishing effort, Geographical distribution, Fishing moratorium

journal/newspaper article

Pulse fishing may be superior to selective fishing (1988-01-01)

H. I. McCallum
[link]: <https://espace.library.uq.edu.au/view/UQ:711702>

Pulse fishing, or fishing heavily at regular intervals rather than continually, has often been suggested to produce higher yields than constant fishing with a lower effort. Existing models, however, are largely based on the assumption that the gear selectivity cannot be adjusted. In many...

Cite as | Export

Area: Fishing effort, Geographical distribution, Fishing moratorium

journal/newspaper article

This visualization was created by [Open Knowledge Maps](#). For more information [read our FAQs](#).

Nivo objave

[Free full text available](#) Article English, French ID: <doi:doaj.org/article:b3c0bec11153456... > · DOI: <10.1051/e3sconf/202337602032> Where these data come from ⓘ

Nomadic camp as an innovative way to preserve national identity

Authors [Sleptsov Yury](#), [Neustroeva Anna](#), [Shergina Tuyaara](#), [Kozhurova Anna](#), [Permyakova Anna](#), + 1

Publication Date: 2023-01-01
Last GoTriple update: 2023-04-12
Publisher: EDP Sciences
Provider: Doaj
License: Undefined
Conditions of Access: Undefined

Disciplines
Education | Social Anthropology and Ethnology

Keywords
indigenous peoples of the north | evens (lamuts)
school-age children | nomadic camp | ecology
environmental education | traditional education
ethnopedagogisation

TRIPLE Vocabulary tags
Children | Economics | Education | Environmental education
Experience | Games | Identity (Philosophical concept)
Industries | Informal sector (Economics)
Language and languages | Learning | National characteristics
Nationalism | Indigenous peoples | New and old | Possibility
Republics | Vocational education | View less ^

Switch tags language English ▾

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Abstract

The article considers the process of introducing new forms of temporary children's associations during summer vacation days for children from indigenous peoples of the north, the Even people, which implies an ecological expedition of children from the Moma ulus of the Republic of Sakha (Yakutia) to study the

Orodje za označevanje Pundit

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rs > OBP collection > Introducing Vigilant Audiences

OpenBook Publishers Open

Notes on Contributors

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INTRODUCING VIGILANT AUDIENCES | Daniel Trottler, Rashid Gabdulhakov, Qian Huang

Introducing Vigilant Audiences

Daniel Trottler, Rashid Gabdulhakov et Qian Huang

p. 1-23

TEXTE BIBLIOGRAPHIE NOTES AUTEURS ILLUSTRATIONS

TEXTE INTÉGRAL

1 In nearly any context, people are attentive and judgemental when it comes to the affairs of others. Vigilant audiences entail a range of phenomena, span geographic areas and vary in their motivations as well as their affiliations. This watching can escalate to vigilantism if audiences witness something that demands a response. We understand digitally mediated vigilantism to include practices where citizens (or digital media users more generally) are offended by other citizen actions, and retaliate through practices and repertoires that include mobile devices and social platforms

FRANÇAIS Partager Tiziana Lombardo

Tout OpenEdition

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Semantic relations

- identifies
- identifies
- is related to
- describes
- has author
- has type
- cites
- quotes
- replies to
- represents the date

ok

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Druge možnosti platforme

Uporabniški profil

- avtorstvo objav
- osebna priporočila
- javni profil
- kontakt z drugimi uporabniki
- povezava z orodjem Pundit

The screenshot shows a user profile for Agnieszka Szulińska. At the top, there are status indicators: 'Open to collaboration' (in a green box), 'Registered profile', and 'Researcher'. The profile picture is on the left, followed by the name 'Agnieszka Szulińska'. Below the name, it says 'Registered on GoTriple: 2022/09/04' and 'Spoken languages: English, Polish, Russian'. On the right, there is a 'Contact me on Mattermost' button and a 'Share this profile' link with social media icons for Facebook, LinkedIn, and Twitter. Below the profile header, there are tabs for 'Overview' and 'Documents' (with a count of 4). The 'About' section contains a paragraph: 'Agnieszka Szulińska (née Kochańska, b. 1989) graduated from Cardinal Stefan Wyszyński University in Warsaw with an MA degree in Polish Philology (specialization in scholarly editing). She prepares a'. To the right, the 'Disciplines' section lists 'Linguistics', 'Literature', 'Art and Art History', 'Cultural Heritage and Museology', and 'Education'.

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Gunda Nassim

Account settings

Welcome to you account settings page Gunda.

Main information

Main information like name, email, location and much more

What type of user are you

Your professional interests, also known as Disciplines

Your interests

Your professional interests, also known as Disciplines

Notifications

Decide which notifications you want to receive and how often

Experience

Your current affiliation and your past professional experience

Education

School and university experience

Links and other accounts

Links to your social networks profiles and other personal websites

Password

Change the password to access your GoTriple account

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Druge možnosti platforme

Množično financiranje preko platforme [WeMakelt](https://wemakeit.com)

Več informacij: <https://wemakeit.com/pages/operas>

Ukrainka

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Science, Publishing, and Literature

Support to Ukrainian Editors

by Pierre Mounier, Caroline, and mmaryl

The war in Ukraine is impacting our colleagues in scholarly publishing - We set up the Supporting Ukrainian Editorial Staff program to provide editorial staff in Ukraine with the help they need

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Več informacij: <https://www.meoh.io/tbs>

Telefonska aplikacija: <https://meoh-integration.nurogate.com/api/v1/stores>

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Več informacij

Informacije za ponudnike podatkov

Priročnik za ponudnike podatkov: https://gotriple.eu/docs/gotriple-handbook-v1_0.pdf

Navodila za vključevanje novih ponudnikov preko spletne aplikacije: https://gotriple.eu/docs/your_data_in_gotriple-v1_0.pdf

Video vodniki za uporabnike

TRIPLE Video Tutorials: <https://www.youtube.com/playlist?list=PL2UW3hSUQBFOzNo8H8nDRivURieOQQ5nl>

Uporabniška dokumentacija

De Santis, Luca, Cau, Fabrizio, Giacomi, Danilo, Agosta, Tony, Homo, Julien, Ardizzone, Valeria, & Lamata Martínez, Ignacio. (2023). TRIPLE Deliverable D4.4 Technical and User Documentation for the TRIPLE system (Draft). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7708784>

Orodje Pundit

Tiziana Lombardo, Sona Arasteh, Giulio Andreini and Lottie Provost (2022). The GoTriple Pundit Annotation Tool Training. Version 1.0.0. DARIAH-Campus. [Webinar recording]. https://campus.dariah.eu/id/b2dmiKL0Qk_LWg-FzNcgO

Množično financiranje

Zbirka nasvetov, informacij in virov: <https://project.gotriple.eu/crowdfunding-initiative/>

TRIPLE Open Science Training Series

Katalog usposabljanj: <https://project.gotriple.eu/triple-open-science-training-series/>

The TRIPLE Training Series Decision Tree

To support you in finding the relevant training materials, we created a clickable decision tree. In the layer "I am" you can select via clicking on the node in which group you would see yourself (SSH researcher or support personnel or infrastructure developer). Next you decide in the "I want" which goals you have, e.g., I want... to fit EU requirements. In the next layer, the recommended training sessions are displayed (e.g., Copyright and Academia in the Digital Era); the titles of the training sessions are clickable and redirect you to the website where the training materials are available.

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